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ABSTRACT

Proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET) and hydrogen-atom transfer (HAT) reactions, collectively called H-atom abstraction (HAA) reactions, play critical roles in biological processes and modern organic synthesis. The kinetics of these processes can align with the principles described in the renowned Marcus cross relation (MCR), a framework initially formulated to describe electron transfer mechanisms. The MCR provides an outstanding link between the kinetics of HAA reactions involving two distinct reactants and two related auxiliary self-exchange reactions—each between a molecule of one of the reactants and its conjugated radical. In this study, we investigate the applicability and limitations of the canonical MCR across over 300 HAA reactions, providing a comprehensive theoretical analysis. Our findings reveal the need for an enhanced framework that incorporates “off-diagonal” thermodynamic factors—asynchronicity and frustration. Of these factors, asynchronicity, which quantifies the imbalance between the proton vs electron transfer components of the reaction, is identified as the dominant contributor to the improved predictive accuracy of the MCR. Notably, the incorporation of off-diagonal thermodynamics yields a more pronounced enhancement for HAT reactions than for PCET-like HAA reactions. As a corollary, the model also describes a so-called *pseudoinverted* region, in which more exergonic reactions feature higher free energy barriers even though the thermodynamic driving force is not so large as it is required for the proper inverted region well-known from the original Marcus theory. This advancement offers a refined theoretical basis for understanding H-atom abstraction mechanisms and underscores the importance of off-diagonal effects in HAA chemistry.

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INTRODUCTION

H-atom transfer (HAT) and proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET) reactions, frequently grouped under a broader term of H-atom abstraction (HAA) chemistry,^{1–3} have been recognized for decades to drive many important processes in nature, from PCET-promoted energy conversion pathways, such as a cellular respiration chain,^{4,5} to enzymatic HAT/PCET-initiated transformations, yielding a plethora of compounds essential for living organisms.^{6–10} From an industrial and societal point of view, it is interesting to note

that intensive development of efficient and inexpensive HAT/PCET-based processes, such as electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ or N₂^{11–14} or photoredox catalytic synthesis of high-value organic and natural compounds,^{15–20} are also currently under way.

Despite amazing advances in synthetic chemistry,^{21,22} a major problem remains: a precise control of chemo- or regioselectivity of a single C–H bond in the presence of many such bonds in organic molecules. Two of the very few fruitful examples of nonintuitive regioselectivity were given by MacMillan who succeeded in targeting a strong C–H bond avoiding cleavage of a proximal weaker

bond^{23,24} and by Bietti who achieved highly selective C–H bond oxygenation at remote methylenic sites.²⁵ In both cases, the authors identified polarity match between a C–H bond and an oxidant as a driving factor for selectivity.^{26,27} However, this approach was built upon qualitative guidelines, and its predictable extension to different carbon skeletons is currently not accessible by any means other than “hit or miss.” We note in passing that an interesting approach for the selective functionalization of a C–H bond was reported by Rovis; in this case, the strategy relies on the Curtin–Hammett principle.²⁸

From the theoretical point of view, HAT and PCET are mechanistically distinct. HAT is a strongly adiabatic reaction, in which the reactant and product state gradually mix along the reaction coordinate and this continuous admixture creates a well-characterized and barrier-determining transition state on the way to product. In contrast, PCET is characterized by a non-adiabatic (weak) coupling between these states with an abrupt change in electronic structure in the vicinity of the top of the barrier. Therefore, it is impossible to locate the transition state and the standard Eyring’s transition state theory becomes essentially inapplicable. Reactions where electron and proton do not share the same donor and/or acceptor site are typically PCET.^{29,30} For these, a sophisticated theory developed by Hammes-Schiffer describes the rate constant as a function of several key reaction variables, including overlaps of proton vibrational wave functions associated with the reactant and product states.^{31–35} Armed with this theory, Hammes-Schiffer and Mayer demonstrated, for example, the existence of the famous Marcus inversion region for PCET chemistry, where a reaction with a stronger thermodynamic driving force (more stable products) has a slower rate.³⁶

Recently, one of our groups has developed a simpler theoretical model that links HAA reactivity to three-component thermodynamics, consisting of the free energy of reaction, reinforced with asynchronicity, and frustration, the latter two being the so-called off-diagonal thermodynamic terms determined by the energetics of two-step electron transfer/proton transfer (ET/PT) and proton transfer/electron transfer (PT/ET) pathways.^{37,38} In particular, the influence of asynchronicity on the preference of ET over PT (and vice versa) in a single-barrier HAA reaction has already been verified by several experimental groups.^{39–46}

Last but not least, Mayer experimentally demonstrated that a bimolecular PCET reaction satisfies one of the most remarkable relations in chemistry: Marcus cross relation (MCR).^{47,48} It is nearly 40 years since Marcus derived the relation between the rate constant for ET between two different reactants (X and Y) and the rate constants of two self-exchange ETs.⁴⁸ In these self-exchange reactions, an electron is exchanged between two identical reactants (i.e., between X and X, and between Y and Y). Namely, the MCR is given as

$$k_{XY} \approx \sqrt{k_{XX}k_{YY}K_{XY}f_q}, \quad (1)$$

where the rate constant of the *mixed* XY reaction is a geometric mean of the rate constants of two *self-exchange* XX and YY reactions and K_{XY} is the equilibrium constant of the mixed reaction. The factor f_q corresponds to a quadratic term as present in the Marcus model for the ET barrier and is frequently omitted since it is often close to 1. Sometimes, the MCR from Eq. (1) is refined to the form⁴⁸

$$k_{XY} \approx \left(\sqrt{k_{XX}k_{YY}K_{XY}f_{qw}} \right) \xi, \quad (2)$$

where ξ is a correction to the rate of a mixed reaction due to the difference in the formation energies of the reactant and product complexes in the mixed and self-exchange reactions and f_{qw} represents the quadratic correction to the linearized Marcus model for the barrier and also explicitly accounts for the correction related to the formation free energies of the reactant and product complexes in both XY and XX/YY bimolecular reactions. While the validity of the MCR for PCET reactions is impressive because the MCR was strictly speaking derived only for ET (admittedly, the number of tested PCET reactions was still quite limited), some important aspects remain fully unexplored. *How well does MCR perform for bimolecular PCET vs bimolecular HAT reactions? Do asynchronicity and frustration, two off-diagonal thermodynamic factors missing in Eqs. (1) and (2), play an important and missing part of MCR? If yes, how?* These questions, central to this study, are addressed in the following sections.

COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

H-atom abstraction energetics

Geometry optimizations of MeCN-solvated systems were carried out using the ORCA 5.0.4 program^{49,50} at the B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-SVP/CPCM(acetonitrile) level of theory, which includes (i) the B3LYP⁵¹ functional, (ii) the Grimme’s correction to dispersion with Becke–Johnson damping (D3BJ),⁵² (iii) the def2-SVP basis set,⁵³ and (iv) the CPCM implicit solvation model of the acetonitrile solvent.⁵⁴ Calculations were further expedited by expanding the Coulomb integrals in an auxiliary basis set employing the RIJCOSX approximation.⁵⁵

The initial Cartesian coordinates of all studied systems were generated from the SMILES⁵⁶ string representation of molecules using RDKit.⁵⁷ The MMFF optimizer in RDKit was employed to refine the initial geometric estimates for structures of the half-reaction cycles and for the transition state (TS) structures. In case of TSs, the automated computational pipeline for the geometry optimization includes the following three steps:

- (i) Constrained optimization using the PBE functional^{58,59} with constrained $r(X-H)/r(Y-H)$ ratio to equal to 1 (r denotes bond length). This was achieved by inserting a dummy atom Q perpendicular to the X–H–Y plane and fixing the following four angles: X–H–Q, Y–H–Q (both 90° by construction), X–Q–H, and Y–Q–H.
- (ii) Constrained optimization at the B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-SVP/CPCM(acetonitrile) level.
- (iii) Full optimization using the B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-SVP/CPCM(acetonitrile) level.

An analogous automated protocol was applied to the half-reaction cycle structures, with the second step omitted and no constraints imposed.

The reactant and product complexes were optimized starting from the structures obtained from a small dislocation of the transferred H-atom in TSs [by 0.1 Å to reactant complex (RC) and product complex (PC)]. For all final optimized structures, the frequency calculation (at 298 K and 1 atm; ideal-gas approximation) was done to verify that the structure is a minimum or a first-order saddle point (in case of TS) on the potential energy

surface and to obtain thermal factors necessary for the evaluation of the Gibbs free energy of the system. Namely, Gibbs free energies were calculated according to the following equation: $G = E_{el,solv} + [E_{ZPVE} + pV + RT\ln Q]$, where $E_{el,solv}$ is the potential energy of a MeCN-solvated system and $[E_{ZPVE} + pV + RT\ln Q]$ corresponds to the thermal enthalpic and entropic contributions to the solute energy; E_{ZPVE} and Q are the zero-point vibrational energy and molecular partition function, respectively.

Wherever the molarity is changed, for example, in the transition from separated reactants to RC or TS, a value of $1.9\Delta n$ kcal mol⁻¹ has been applied to correct the computed Gibbs free energy change ΔG to the 1 mol L⁻¹ standard state. A value of 1.9 kcal mol⁻¹ corresponds to the conversion of a 1 bar standard state in the gas phase to 1 mol L⁻¹ concentration in solution at 298 K; Δn is the change in the number of moles. It is worth noting that some reaction sets examined in this study are categorized as PCET-like HAAs (as discussed later), yet exhibiting localized transition states optimized within the adiabatic approximation. This allowed us to apply the transition-state theory to analyze trends in barrier evolution across related systems.

Intrinsic bond orbital (IBO) analyses

Intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) structures were derived from the corresponding TSs using the Gaussian 16 Rev C.01 program,⁶⁰ employing the same computational level as used for geometry optimization. To examine the electron flow, the electronic structures of all IRC geometries were recalculated using the ORCA 5.0.4 program,^{49,50} at the same level of theory. IBOs were then generated using IboView (iboexp = 2).^{61,62}

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The equilibrium and the rate constants for the reaction

Each elementary reaction is defined by two important parameters: the equilibrium constant (K), which reflects the

thermodynamic driving force for the conversion of reactants into products, and the rate constant (k), which measures the speed of this conversion. While the constant K is connected to the relative stability of the products with respect to the reactants,

$$K = e^{-\Delta G_0/RT}, \quad (3)$$

with ΔG_0 to be the free energy of reaction (as shown in Fig. 1), the rate constant relates to the relative stability of the transition state with respect to the reactants,

$$k = Ae^{-\Delta G^\ddagger/RT}, \quad (4)$$

where ΔG^\ddagger is the free-energy barrier for the elementary reaction, as illustrated in Fig. 1; the pre-exponential factor A in this study is not specified.

Mixed and self-exchange HAA reactions and their free-energy profiles

Elementary bimolecular HAA reaction in solution decomposes into three events, including (i) the association of separated reactants X-H and Y• to the RC, (ii) the transfer of a hydrogen atom (or an H⁺/e⁻ pair) between X-H and Y• leading via the TS to the formation of the PC, and (iii) the dissociation of the PC to the separated products Y-H and X•.⁶³ The right part of Fig. 1 illustrates the free-energy profile of a mixed reaction, in which the H-atom donor differs chemically from the H-atom acceptor, which generally leads to a release or consumption of the free energy of the reaction (and therefore generally $\Delta G_0 \neq 0$). The left part of Fig. 1 shows a free energy profile for a self-exchange HAA reaction, in which a hydrogen atom is exchanged between the same reactants (between X-H and X• or Y-H and Y•) and therefore the reaction experiences no thermodynamic driving force, as the free energy of products equals to the free energy of reactants ($\Delta G_{0,XX} = \Delta G_{0,YY} = 0$). For such elementary bimolecular self-exchange HAA reactions, the barrier is

$$\Delta G_{XX}^\ddagger = w_{R,XX} + \Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS}, \quad (5)$$

FIG. 1. Illustrative free-energy profile for an elementary bimolecular HAA reaction between X-H and Y• (right) along with the definition of key quantities used in this study: $w_{R,XY}$ —the free energy of formation of the RC from two separated reactants, $w_{P,XY}$ —the free energy of formation of the PC from two separated reactants, the free energy of reaction in going from the separated reactants to the separated products ($[\Delta G_0] \downarrow 0$), and the free energy of activation in going from separated reactants to TS (ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger) and from RC to TS ($\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS}$). The self-exchange reactions (left) are featured by $\Delta G_0 = 0$ kcal mol⁻¹ and $w_R = w_P$.

with $\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger,RC\rightarrow TS}$ to be the RC-to-TS component of the total reaction barrier.

The free-energy barrier of the mixed XY reaction ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} can be decomposed using the linearized Marcus-type model for the barrier,⁴⁸ assuming that the association of the reactants is in pre-equilibrium,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} &= w_{R,XY} + \Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger,RC\rightarrow TS} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(w_{R,XY} + w_{P,XY}) + \Delta G_{intrinsic,XY}^{\ddagger,RC\rightarrow TS} + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} \\ &= \Delta G_{intrinsic,XY}^{\ddagger} + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2},\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

with the parameters except for $\Delta G_{intrinsic,XY}^{\ddagger,RC\rightarrow TS}$ provided in Fig. 1; the intrinsic barrier $\Delta G_{intrinsic,XY}^{\ddagger}$ is the *hypothetical* barrier of the mixed HAA reaction if it were ergo-neutral, i.e., the effect of the thermodynamics on the barrier $\frac{\Delta G_0}{2}$ would be eliminated; analogously, the $\Delta G_{intrinsic,XY}^{\ddagger,RC\rightarrow TS}$ is the RC-to-TS component of this *hypothetical* barrier.

Marcus cross relation from Eq. (1) and its refinement from Eq. (2)

The well-known Eq. (1) combined with Eqs. (3) and (4) yields the Marcus cross relation in the following form:

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \approx \Delta G_{MCR}^{\ddagger} \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_q) + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + C, \quad (7)$$

where the barrier of the HAA reaction between X and Y is given as a sum of three terms:

- (i) the average of the two self-exchange barriers $\frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger})$,

- (ii) the quadratic correction term as mentioned above (and derived in the [supplementary material](#)) has the following form:

$$-\frac{1}{2}RT \ln f_q = \frac{1}{8} \frac{\Delta G_0^2}{\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}}, \quad (8)$$

- (iii) the barrier contribution arising from the free energy of the mixed reaction $\frac{\Delta G_0}{2}$, and

- (iv) the remaining contribution $C = -1/2RT \ln(A_{XX}A_{YY}/A_{XY}^2)$ is the term depending on the pre-exponential factor A from Eq. (4). In this study, if not stated otherwise, C is neglected for the following reasons: (i) for adiabatic reactions (such as HATs), which are well described by Eyring's transition state theory, C is strictly 0 and (ii) for non-adiabatic reactions (such as PCETs), A typically ranges between 10^{12} and 10^{13} s^{-1} ; this corresponds to a typical variation in the C term of $\sim 2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, or likely even less.

Equation (2) can be re-expressed in terms of free energies by combining it with Eqs. (3) and (4) so that

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \approx \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) + \Delta w - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw}) + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + C, \quad (9)$$

with

$$\Delta w = \frac{1}{2}(w_{R,XY} + w_{P,XY}) - \frac{1}{2}(w_{R,XX} + w_{R,YY}), \quad (10)$$

where the quantities w_R and w_P are the free energies of RC and PC formation defined in Fig. 2, respectively; note that Eq. (2) contains this factor in the form of $\xi = e^{-\Delta w/RT}$. The meaning of the correction term f_{qw} is explained earlier in the text (its derivation provided in the [supplementary material](#)), while its explicit form is as follows:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [(\Delta G_{e^-} - \Delta G_{H^+}) - (\Delta G_{e^-} - \Delta G_{H^+})]$$

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [(\Delta G_{e^-} + \Delta G_{H^+}) - (\Delta G_{e^-} + \Delta G_{H^+})]$$

FIG. 2. Full-reaction thermodynamic cycle for HAA between the H-atom donor X-H and the H-atom abstractor Y^\bullet , decomposed into two half-reaction cycles: one for Y^\bullet (in blue) and one for X^\bullet (in red), respectively. The key energy parameters for each of the two half-reaction cycles, such as the free energy of one-electron reduction (ΔG_{e^-}) and the free energy of protonation (ΔG_{H^+}), are given. Of these, asynchronicity and frustration, two full-reaction off-diagonal thermodynamic quantities, are defined (right of the figure). The thermodynamic driving force for HAA that is the free energy of reaction ΔG_0 is also indicated. Note that the ET and PT intermediates formed along the sequential off-diagonal pathways are marked by the circles. The additional details on the calculations of thermodynamic properties associated with the half-reaction/full-reaction cycles are also given in Figure S1.

$$-\frac{1}{2}RT \ln f_{qw} = \frac{(\Delta G_0 + w_{P,XY} - w_{R,XY})^2}{8(\Delta G_{XX}^\ddagger + \Delta G_{YY}^\ddagger - w_{R,XX} - w_{R,XY})}. \quad (11)$$

We note in passing that when Δw is explicitly combined with the expressions for ΔG_{XX}^\ddagger and ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from Eqs. (5) and (6), Eq. (8) is then transformed to

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS} \approx \Delta G_{MCR}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS} \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS}) - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw}) + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + C, \quad (12)$$

describing the relation between the RC-to-TS barriers of the mixed and self-exchange reactions. Note that the RC/PC formation energies are usually difficult to obtain experimentally and therefore Eqs. (2) and (9) are less practically applicable, as compared to simplified Eqs. (1) and (7).

A three-component thermodynamic model linking thermodynamics and kinetics

From Fig. 2, three thermodynamically equivalent HAA pathways exist—one of them is a *diagonal* pathway in which electron and proton are transferred from the donor to the acceptor concertedly (in one single step), while the remaining two are *off-diagonal* pathways, in which electron and proton are transferred sequentially (in two steps). One off-diagonal pathway leads through the ET intermediate (the right upper corner of Fig. 2) and the other through the PT intermediate (the left lower corner of Fig. 2). All three HAA scenarios share the identical free energy of reaction ΔG_0 , which drives a reaction. From Refs. 37 and 38, the energetics associated with the off-diagonal pathways determines the two thermodynamic factors, asynchronicity (η) and frustration (σ). The former corresponds to the free energy difference between the ET and PT intermediates and controls the difference in the ET vs PT progress at the single-barrier HAA transition state;³⁷ the latter accounts for the overall (in)accessibility of the ET and PT intermediates, which co-influences the earliness/lateness of both ET/PT at TS (along with ΔG_0).³⁸ By definition, all thermodynamic terms, η , σ , and ΔG_0 , are equal to 0 for self-exchange reactions.

The two key off-diagonal thermodynamic quantities, η and σ , together with ΔG_0 , co-affect the height of the single-step HAA barrier of the mixed XY reaction (ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from Fig. 1). This finding is quantified using the linearized Marcus-type model for the reaction barrier,

$$\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + \Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger + \Delta G_{00}^\ddagger, \quad (13)$$

where the single-step HAA barrier consists of three terms with the latter two being

$$\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger = \frac{|\sigma|}{4} - \frac{|\eta|}{4}, \quad (14)$$

and ΔG_{00}^\ddagger containing all reaction coordinate dependent factors, including the free-energies of the formation of RC and PC, so if we account for them explicitly, then $\Delta G_{00}^\ddagger = \frac{1}{2}(w_{R,XY} + w_{P,XY}) + \Delta G_{00}^{\ddagger,RC \rightarrow TS}$. The sum of the second and third terms yields $\Delta G_{intrinsic}^\ddagger$, as defined by Eq. (6).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PCET vs HAT modus operandi of HAAs

The mechanistic distinction between PCET and HAT reactions lies in how the electronic states involved in bond rearrangements mix along the reaction coordinate. According to valence bond theory, a non-interacting (diabatic) state preserves its electronic character as the molecular geometry changes. Within this framework, two diabatic states along the reaction coordinate are defined: the reactant state and the product state. An interacting state—whether adiabatic or non-adiabatic—is described as a geometry-dependent linear combination of these diabatic states. Consequently, the ground-state reaction barrier in the adiabatic (or non-adiabatic) representation arises from strong (or weak) configuration mixing between the reactant and product diabatic states, whose potential energy surfaces intersect near the transition state. The energy difference between the TS and the point of intersection can vary widely—from tens of kcal mol⁻¹ in HAT reactions to less than 1 kcal mol⁻¹ in “pure” PCET.

In the latter case, mixing between the reactant and product states occurs only within a very narrow region near the intersection, preventing from the localization of the TS, and therefore, such limiting scenarios (i.e., “pure” PCETs) are not presented in the current study. Instead, the HAA reactions examined here span from PCET-like reactions with a small adiabatic coupling, such as phenoxy/phenol system³⁴ (where TS remains well localizable), to HAT.

One guideline that helps distinguish PCET-like HAAs from HAT is the spatial separation of the proton and/or electron donor and acceptor. Greater spatial separation is associated with a lower degree of configuration interaction between the diabatic reactant and product states, resulting in the PCET-like modus operandi of HAA. This separation (or a difference in transfer coordinate) can also be effectively tracked through the analysis of intrinsic bond orbitals, as discussed below, allowing us to classify the studied HAA reactions as either PCET-like or HAT reactions.

Importantly, the distinction between PCET and HAT reactions lies not only in the extent of mixing between diabatic states—and consequently the localizability of the transition state structures—but also in the pre-exponential factor (represented by the term C in the equations above), as previously discussed. Nevertheless, each set of HAA reactions encompasses closely related processes, making this approximation reasonable for examining reactivity trends across similar systems.

Formulation of Marcus cross relation for HAA including asynchronicity and frustration factors

The off-diagonal thermodynamics is an important component of HAA reactivity in mixed XY systems as has been investigated computationally in the Srncec laboratory^{37,38,64,65} and experimentally by others.^{39–46} Therefore, we may suspect that the canonical MCR Eq. (1) can be enhanced to account for the effect of the off-diagonal thermodynamics comprising asynchronicity and frustration, which introduced in the section titled “PCET vs HAT modus operandi of HAAs” and which is not a part of the self-exchange HAA reactions. Namely, we suggest modifying Eq. (1) to

$$k_{XY} \approx \sqrt{k_{XX}k_{YY}K_{XY}f_{qgXY}}, \quad (15)$$

where all terms except g_{XY} are from Eq. (1) and

$$g_{XY} = e^{-\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}/RT} \quad (16)$$

is the contribution to the reaction rate associated with the off-diagonal thermodynamic component of the reaction barrier of a mixed XY reaction; $\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}$ is explicitly defined by Eq. (14). Equation (15), key to this work, is then re-expressed in terms of free energies as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} &\approx \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{|\sigma|}{4} - \frac{|\eta|}{4}\right) \\ &= \Delta G_{MCR}^{\ddagger} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Clearly, ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} is newly approximated by adding one half of the off-diagonal thermodynamic barrier component to the original MCR barrier from Eq. (7). The term C is omitted (see above) if not mentioned otherwise.

Introducing the off-diagonal correction from Eq. (14) to the original MCR refined using the free energies of RC and PC formation in both self-exchange and mixed reactions (Δw , from Eq. (10)), yields the following equation:

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \approx \Delta G_{MCR}^{\ddagger} + \Delta w - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw}) + \frac{1}{2}\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}. \quad (18)$$

This new MCR model, which incorporates off-diagonal thermodynamics [Eqs. (17) and (18)], differs from the original off-diagonal thermodynamic model of Ref. 38 presented by Eq. (13) in the treatment of $\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}$. Here, $\Delta G_{offdiag}^{\ddagger}$ is scaled by a factor of 1/2. Through a closer comparison of the two models, we can reformulate ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} from Eq. (13) in terms of the quantities used in Eq. (17) to reveal that a fraction of the off-diagonal contribution is now incorporated in the reaction coordinate dependent contribution ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} ,

$$\Delta G_{00}^{\ddagger} = \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{|\sigma|}{4} - \frac{|\eta|}{4}\right). \quad (19)$$

The presence of a fraction of the off-diagonal term in ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} can be attributed to the effect of asynchronicity (and frustration) on the adiabatic coupling. This interconnection of the models goes well in line with the qualitative observation from Ref. 65, where the data led us to the conclusion that ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} increases with an increasing asynchronicity via its effect on adiabatic coupling (AC). The effect of asynchronicity on AC was rationalized in Ref. 65 as follows: AC represents the interaction between PT and ET components in the HAA. Given that thermodynamic asynchronicity governs the degree of concertedness between the PT and ET in the HAA, the role of AC is expected to diminish as the reaction transitions from a less asynchronous to a more asynchronous HAA process. The formulation presented in Eq. (19), along with its potential extensions or refinement, lies beyond the scope of the current work and is the subject of ongoing investigation in our laboratory.

The inverted and pseudo-inverted regions

A key characteristic of a non-linearized (quadratic) Marcus-type model for reactivity, including Eq. (18), is its dependence on ΔG_0 , which appears in two terms: $\frac{\Delta G_0}{2}$ and $-\frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw})$, the latter of which is proportional to the square of ΔG_0 as defined by Eq. (11). As ΔG_0 becomes more negative, the reaction barrier decreases,

reaching its minimum (the $\frac{\Delta G_0}{2}$ term dominates and thus defines the so-called normal region). Beyond this point, as ΔG_0 continues to decrease further, the barrier rises again, marking the transition into the so-called inverted region dominated by $-\frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw}) \propto (\Delta G_0)^2$. According to Eqs. (17) and (18), which account for the influence of off-diagonal thermodynamics, it is theoretically possible to observe a pseudo-inverted region while remaining within the normal region in terms of ΔG_0 . This may occur, for example, due to the asynchronicity factor, provided its effect is significantly more favorable in less exergonic reactions, thereby outweighing the influence of $\Delta G_0/2$. While all reactions studied in this work are within the normal region for ΔG_0 , there are cases that fall into the pseudo-inverted region (see below).

The studied reaction sets

In this study, we examined 307 HAA reactions, which cover broad range of various thermodynamic properties of the reactants and their mixed HAA reactions (Table S1–S3). The reactions are organized into five sets (labeled A–E in Fig. 3), each of them involving a unique series of related substrates (H-atom donors). The reaction sets are further divided into subsets based on the specific oxidant (H-atom acceptor) used, such as A1 and A2, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

According to the IBO analyses presented in Fig. S2, these sets fall into two categories dependent on the transfer coordinates of proton and electron. In sets A and B, IBO analyses reveal that during the reaction, the α electron from the X–H bond remains localized on the donor atom, ultimately resulting in the formation of a radical X^{\bullet} . Meanwhile, the β electron from the X–H bond is transferred to the acceptor atom of Y^{\bullet} along with the proton, forming a new Y–H σ bond. This indicates that proton and electron are transferred as one unit—as a hydrogen atom—classifying sets A and B as HAT reactions. Conversely, in reaction sets C–E, the proton and electron do not transfer to the same site of the acceptor, characterizing these sets as PCET-like HAA reactions (Fig. S1).

More specifically, the reaction set A includes 126 HAT reactions between 18 para-substituted toluenes and eight different organic (carbon-, nitrogen-, and oxygen-based) radicals. Set B contains 77 HAT reactions involving 17 para-substituted phenols and five organic (carbon- and nitrogen-based) radicals. Set C features 27 PCET-like HAA reactions between 17 para-substituted phenols and the two organic radicals, while set D covers 53 PCET-like HAA reactions between p,p' -disubstituted diphenylamines and two organic radicals. Finally, set E involves 24 PCET-like HAA reactions between p,p' -disubstituted carbazoles and the phenoxyl radical.

Performance of the MCR approximation across four different levels

In Fig. 4, we evaluate the accuracy of the MCR approximation across four different levels, using the complete set of 307 HAA reactions presented in Fig. 3. Initially, we observed that the simplest and widely recognized MCR form from Eq. (1) delivers only moderate performance [Fig. 4(a)], with HAT datasets showing the poorest agreement. At this level of approximation, the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r^2) appears satisfactory at 0.81 (0.64 for HAT datasets vs 0.91 for PCET-like datasets). However, the additional statistical metrics—the mean absolute error (MAE)

FIG. 3. Reaction sets (A–E) examined in this study and their subdivision into subsets (e.g., **A1** and **A2**). Each set is defined by a series of related substrates, while the subset for a certain series of substrates is defined by the H-atom abstractor. **A–B** include HAT reactions and **C–E** contain PCET-like HAA reactions. Thermodynamic properties of all the reactants and the energetics of the associated mixed and self-exchange HAA reactions are provided in Tables S1–S3.

and the standard deviation of absolute errors (s), both presented in Fig. 4—along with the distribution of reactions within a certain error range shown in Fig. S3, point to significant shortcomings in the model.

As shown in Fig. 4(b), the refined model from Eq. (9), which incorporates corrections for RC/PC formation free energies, is an improvement over the previous model. This is evident from the comparison of Fig. 4(b) with Fig. 4(a) and from their corresponding statistical metrics (e.g., $r^2 = 0.81$ vs 0.9). There is a notable improvement in the description of HAT reactions passing to the model in Fig. 4(b), though there is still room for further enhancement. Remarkably, the model from Eq. (17) in Fig. 4(c), which extends the basic MCR framework from Eq. (1) by including off-diagonal thermodynamic effects, achieves exceptional accuracy (e.g., $r^2 = 0.93$), considerably improving the space of HAT reactions. It outperforms the model from Fig. 4(b) with RC/PC formation corrections, as evidenced by visual inspection and the comparison of all statistical indicators. It is important to emphasize that the off-diagonal term brings the correlation slopes for the sets closer to the ideal value of 1. Inclusion of both corrections, off-diagonal thermodynamics and RC/PC formation energies from Eq. (18), yields the highest accuracy across all MCR models, regardless of whether they are applied to HAT or PCET-like HAA chemical spaces [cf. Fig. 4(d); $r^2 = 0.95$]. From Fig.

S3, over 80% of reactions treated by off-diagonal thermodynamics-enhanced models [Figs. 4(b) and 4(c)] fall within an error range of ± 3 kcal mol $^{-1}$. In comparison, the original MCR model from Fig. 4(a) captures only about 60% of reactions within this same error margin.

As a supplementary note, we also assessed the impact of the correction f_{qw} [defined by Eq. (11) and present in Eqs. (9) and (18)] on the results presented in Figs. 4(b) and 4(d). As evidenced by Fig. S4, this correction is close to 1 for the vast majority of cases, indicating a minimal impact on the predicted barrier that is in most cases less than 0.3 kcal mol $^{-1}$. The same applies to f_q [defined by Eq. (8)], which was already omitted in Eqs. (7) and (17), as this factor was explicitly deemed negligible in the literature; the f_q values for the reactions computed in this study are given in Fig. S4.

Although Fig. 4 evidences that off-diagonal thermodynamics plays a significant role in making MCR more predictive, it remains unclear whether this amelioration is primarily driven by asynchronicity, frustration, or a combination of both factors comparably enhancing the original framework. This issue is addressed by Fig. 5. Therein, the left and right plots display the results for the MCR models derived from Eqs (17) and (18), respectively, but with the frustration factor omitted. In both cases, only the $-|\eta|/4$ term is considered in the equation. All statistical metrics are undoubtedly better

FIG. 4. (a) Computed barrier ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger vs original MCR-predicted ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger , as defined by Eq. (7), with $C = 0$. (b) Computed barrier ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger vs MCR-predicted ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from panel (a) corrected by the inclusion of the RC/PC formation energies, as defined by Eq. (9), with $C = 0$. (c) Computed barrier ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger vs MCR-predicted ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from panel (a) corrected by the inclusion of the off-diagonal thermodynamics, as defined by Eq. (17). (d) Computed barrier ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger vs MCR-predicted ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from panel (b) corrected by off-diagonal thermodynamics, as defined by Eq. (18). Each graph is accompanied by the following metrics: r^2 —the Pearson's correlation factor, MAE—the mean absolute error (in kcal mol⁻¹), and s —the standard deviation of absolute errors (in kcal mol⁻¹) and the regression line. The dashed line indicates the perfect match between the MCR-predicted barrier with the computed barrier. The points are color coded to identify reaction sets from Fig. 3.

when the frustration is included, as seen from Fig. 4(c) vs Fig. 5(a) and from Fig. 4(d) vs Fig. 5(b). However, asynchronicity is critical for aligning the correlation slope across each set, making it essential for going beyond the canonical Eq. (1). Notably, for HATs from sets A–B, the asynchronicity-enriched model in Fig. 5 demonstrates reasonable alignment with the perfect match; however, the deviation is substantial with only ~15%, ~30%, and ~40% of HATs in the error range of ± 1 , ± 2 , and ± 3 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. With both corrections on asynchronicity and formation energy included, the model shows improved accuracy (Figs. 5 and S5), although most of the effects were already captured by incorporating asynchronicity alone. It underscores an important role of frustration in the

HAT-like HAA reactions. In contrast, the PCET-like HAA reactions align more closely with the perfect match line, with ~50%, ~85%, and ~100% of PCETs from sets C–E falling within the error range of ± 1 , ± 2 , and ± 3 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively (see also Fig. S5).

The term C , which we did not consider in Eq. (18) and which depends on the pre-exponential factors A from Eq. (4) as shown above in text, can be estimated *a posteriori* as a difference between the enhanced MCR model from the right side of Eq. (18) and the directly calculated barrier ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from the left side of Eq. (18). In this way, the C value for the HAT/PCET-like/all HAA reaction sets (sets A–B/C–E/A–E) is determined to be $1.53 \pm 1.24/1.70 \pm 0.92/1.59 \pm 1.15$ kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

FIG. 5. Computed ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} vs MCR-predicted ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} (a) from Eq. (17) and (b) from Eq. (18) but with the omission of the frustration-dependent term $|\sigma|/4$.

Analytical vs fitted parameters of the enhanced MCR model

The models proposed in this work by Eqs. (17) and (18) can be readily verified using the reaction sets A–E and linear regression fitting procedure against all these datasets at once. The corresponding generalized equations with the fitting parameters α , β , and γ read

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \approx \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_q) + \alpha \Delta G_0 + \beta |\eta| + \gamma |\sigma|, \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \approx \frac{1}{2}(\Delta G_{XX}^{\ddagger} + \Delta G_{YY}^{\ddagger}) + \Delta w - \frac{1}{2}RT \ln(f_{qw}) + \alpha \Delta G_0 + \beta |\eta| + \gamma |\sigma|. \quad (21)$$

As shown in Fig. 6, the optimized parameters α , β , and γ in both models (20) and (21) align quite well with the prefactors in analytical Eqs. (17) and (18), highlighting the robustness and versatility of these analytical formulations.

Notably, the models with the fitting parameters in Fig. 6 (and in the associated Figure S6) provide $\sim 20\%$, $\sim 60\%$, and $\sim 95\%$ of PCET-like HAAs from sets C–E falling within the error range of ± 1 , ± 2 , and ± 3 kcal mol $^{-1}$, respectively (see also Figure S5). Similarly, the HATs from sets A–B also demonstrate reasonable alignment with the perfect match with $\sim 30\%$, $\sim 60\%$, and $\sim 80\%$ – 90% in the error range of ± 1 , ± 2 , and ± 3 kcal mol $^{-1}$, respectively. From this perspective, the accuracy of the fitting model is comparable with the model having the analytical prefactors in Eqs. (17) and (18), as discussed above. To summarize this part, we conclude that the linear regression coefficients optimized for a block of ~ 300 reactions are closely aligned with the analytical coefficients provided by the model from Eqs. (17) and (18), lending support to the validity of the analytical approach. As expected, the fitted coefficients yield a stronger correlation with the specific dataset, since they are tailored to it. However, unlike the

fitted parameters in Eqs. (20) and (21)—which are inherently data-dependent and thus not universally applicable—the analytical model is designed to be generalizable. In this context, the regression model with fitted parameters serves to reinforce the broader applicability and robustness of the analytical model.

For the sake of completeness, we tested the simplified version of Eqs. (20) and (21), where the off-diagonal fitting parameters β and γ are not included, leaving only the fitting parameter α for ΔG_0 . In the case of the simplified variant of Eq. (20), we obtained the fitting parameters: $\alpha = 0.59$, $r^2 = 0.8$, and MAE = 2.9 kcal mol $^{-1}$. For the variant of Eq. (21), the results were $\alpha = 0.61$, $r^2 = 0.9$, and MAE = 2.2 kcal mol $^{-1}$.

Existence of a pseudoinverted region

So far, we studied the performance of the MCR model and its boost after the inclusion of the factors determined by off-diagonal thermodynamics. Armed with this enhanced model, we focused on the set of HAA reaction pairs that do not follow the standard and intuitive linear free energy relationship between ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} and ΔG_0 ($\Delta \Delta G_{XY}^{\ddagger} \propto \Delta \Delta G_0/2$). In particular, we separately examined each of the subsets (as presented in Fig. 3) in search of such pairs, where a reaction with a more negative (or a less positive) ΔG_0 has a higher barrier ΔG_{XY}^{\ddagger} (Fig. 7).

As already discussed above, such counterintuitive behavior (the so-called inverted region) was originally predicted for very negative ΔG_0 values in the field of electron transfer reactions, and only recently it has been proven to exist also in the field of PCET, where a large negative ΔG_0 was achieved through the electronic excitation of one of the PCET reactants, imposing a huge thermodynamic driving force toward the products (~ 50 kcal mol $^{-1}$).⁶⁶ In the case of PCET, the observed inverted behavior was rationalized by decrease of vibronic coupling between the reactant ground state and product excited states.^{66–68}

FIG. 6. (a) Computed ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger vs MCR-like ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from Eq. (17). (b) Comparison of ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger with the MCR-like ΔG_{XY}^\ddagger from Eq. (18).

FIG. 7. Pairs of HAA reactions selected from Fig. 3 and fulfilling the following conditions: (i) a more exergonic reaction by more than 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ ($\Delta\Delta G_0 < -0.5$ kcal mol⁻¹) has a lower barrier by more than 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ ($\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger < 0.5$ kcal mol⁻¹)—which defines the so-called normal region (blue points)—and (ii) a more exergonic reaction by more than 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ ($\Delta\Delta G_0 < -0.5$ kcal mol⁻¹) has a higher barrier by more than 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ ($\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger > 0.5$ kcal mol⁻¹)—which defines the so-called pseudo-inverted region (red points). The threshold of 0.5 was set to pick top 20% pairs featuring most significant free energy differences. These points representing two regions are mapped on the 2D space given by two variables taken from Eq. (18): (left plot) the contribution to $\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger$, arising from differences between reaction asynchronicities ($-\Delta|\eta|/8$) against the contribution to $\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger$ coming from the difference between free energies of reaction ($\Delta\Delta G_0/2$) and (right plot) the $-\Delta|\eta|/8 + \Delta\Delta w$ contribution, where the latter term is related to difference in RC/PC formation energies of both reactions [cf. a precise definition of Δw in Eq. (10)]—against the $\Delta\Delta G_0/2$ contribution. The dashed lines in both plots mark the region where the sum of two variables is 0, that is, there is no joint effect on $\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger$. For the analysis of other factors from Eq. (18) contributing to $\Delta\Delta G_{XY}^\ddagger$ (belonging to the pseudo-inverted region); see Fig. S7.

The presented model suggests that the inverted behavior can be seemingly achieved for much lower thermodynamic driving forces due to other factors related to either off-diagonal thermodynamics (such as asynchronicity) or the reaction coordinate dependent factors. Thus, we call it a pseudo-inverted behavior. While the model from Eq. (18) indeed predicts the existence of the classical

inverted region for very negative ΔG_0 , this region is not reached in this study, as ΔG_0 ranges from the positive to only modestly negative values (Table S3). Instead, this study covers many HAA reaction pairs, which constitute the pseudo-inverted region. In analogy to studies of inverted region, where the only variable parameter is ΔG_0 , our analysis was performed separately for each of the

subsets, featuring a closely related series of reactants. This way the thermodynamic contributions were systematically varied, while other parameters, constituting the intrinsic, system-specific components of the barrier, were fixed. This is in detail analyzed in Figs. 7 and S7, where we characterized pairs by their relative exergonicity, reaction barrier, and relevant barrier contributions. From these figures, it follows that in most of the pairs in the pseudoinverted region (top right corner in plots in Fig. 7), the more exergonic HAA reactions are also less asynchronous. In other words, in this region, the effect of asynchronicity on the barrier is opposing the effect of ΔG_0 and both factors are largely comparable in magnitude or asynchronicity-derived factor dominates over ΔG_0 .

In addition to asynchronicity, in vast majority of cases, the effect of Δw [related to RC/PC formation energies from Eq. (10)] also acts against the effect of ΔG_0 and thus supports the effect of asynchronicity. These two effects appear to be critical for observing the pseudoinverted region in a set of related HAA reactions as shown in the right plot in Fig. 7. Moreover, these factors may be linked to the fact that two reactants exhibit a better polarity match (in Ref. 64, we showed that asynchronicity is a good quantifier of polarity match between the oxidant and X–H bond substrate). The other and less important contributors to the existence of the pseudoinverted region presented in this work are shown in Figure S7.

CONCLUSIONS

In the presented work, we computationally revisited the famous Marcus cross relation (MCR) for H-atom abstraction (HAA) chemistry. In MCR, the rate constant of the HAA reaction between two different reactants, X and Y, is related to the rate constants of two parental self-exchange HAA reactions between the two identical reactants, i.e., between X and X and between Y and Y, as given by Eq. (1) and/or Eq. (2). The MCR incorporates also the free energy of the mixed XY reaction (thermodynamic driving force), which is known to be fundamental to mixed HAA kinetics but, by definition, does not affect the self-exchange reactions. As we demonstrated elsewhere, there are two additional thermodynamic factors, based on the acid–base and redox properties of the two reactants, that jointly influence the kinetics of the mixed XY reactions. These factors, known as asynchronicity and frustration, are collectively termed the off-diagonal thermodynamics and complement the free energy of reaction. Asynchronicity controls the earliness/lateness of electron vs proton transfer (or *vice versa*) within a single-barrier HAA process, which is dictated by the difference in thermodynamic driving forces for the individual electron vs proton transfer processes. Frustration (in addition to the free energy of reaction) contributes to the joint earliness/lateness of the electron and proton transfer, governed by the combined thermodynamic driving forces of the individual electron and proton transfer processes. The two thermodynamic factors are not a part of the self-exchange XX and YY reactions, and therefore, they must be incorporated explicitly into the MCR, in analogy to the free energy of reaction. Using a set of 307 mixed hydrogen atom abstractions (HAAs) and 109 associated self-exchange reactions encompassing both PCET-like HAAs and HATs, we found that off-diagonal thermodynamics is essential for enhancing the original MCR in the space of H-atom abstraction reactions. We also quantified the extent to which off-diagonal

thermodynamics must be integrated into the original MCR to achieve this improvement. In addition, we found that incorporating off-diagonal thermodynamics leads to a greater enhancement of MCR in HAT reactions compared to PCET-like HAAs. Of the two off-diagonal factors, asynchronicity plays a more crucial role in enhancing the MCR, while the inclusion of frustration further improves its quantitative accuracy. The model also allowed to define a so-called *pseudoinverted* region, in which more exergonic reactions feature higher free energy barriers, even though the thermodynamic driving force is not so large as it is required for the proper inverted region well known from the original Marcus theory. This pseudoinverted behavior can be mostly attributed to a joint action of asynchronicity and a term associated with formation energy, overriding the effect of the free energy of the reaction. This advancement offers a refined theoretical basis for understanding the H-atom abstraction mechanisms and underscores the importance of off-diagonal effects in PCET-/HAT-like HAA chemistry.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) contains depiction and Cartesian coordinates of all models (PDF), intrinsic bonding orbital analysis, all thermodynamic characteristics associated with the half-reaction cycles, and the key energetics of the mixed XY, XX and YY HAA reactions (PDF).

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Jan Kovář: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Software (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Erik Andris:** Software (equal). **Zuzanna Wojdyla:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Jishnu Sai Gopinath:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal). **Jakub Klinkovský:** Software (equal). **Radek Fučík:** Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Martin Srnec:** Conceptualization

(equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data are available in DOI:[10.5281/zenodo.14267062](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267062) and/or after reasonable request to the corresponding author.

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